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Abstract

This deliverable report offers details on the development of the GraspOS federated infrastructure, and contains references to the code repositories and the documentation websites of the respective software packages. This is the third (and final) version of the respective deliverable providing refinements and updates to everything reported in D4.4, that has been submitted in August 2024.

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Abbreviation List

- **API:** Application Programming Interface
- **ARC:** "Athena" Research Centre
- **CKAN:** Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
- **DB:** Database
- **DIAL:** Data Interoperability & Access Layer
- **EOSC:** European Open Science Cloud
- **FOMI:** Open & Federated Research Assessment Infrastructure (previously called "Federated Open Metrics Infrastructure")
- **OS:** Open Science
- **OS-aware RRA:** Open-Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment
- **OSAF:** Open Science Assessment Framework, renamed to "SCOPE+i Framework"
- **OWL:** Web Ontology Language
- **QoS:** Quality of Service
- **RA-SKG:** Research Assessment Scientific Knowledge Graphs
- **RDA:** Research Data Alliance
- **RRA:** Responsible Research Assessment
- **SAMOD:** Simplified Agile Methodology for Ontology Development
- **SHACL:** Shapes Constraint Language
- **SKG:** Scientific Knowledge Graphs

- **SKG-IF:** Scientific Knowledge Graphs Interoperability Framework
- **TRL:** Technology Readiness Level
- **UI:** User Interface
- **UNIBO:** University of Bologna
- **URL:** Uniform Resource Locator

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1. Executive Summary

Research assessment plays an important role in various aspects of research, from guiding the hiring and promotion of researchers to policymaking. GraspOS delivers a federated infrastructure, referred to as “FOMI” in the original project plan but now simply called the GraspOS infrastructure, to support research assessment by integrating and providing easy access to a range of valuable resources, including data, tools, services, templates, and guidance materials. The primary focus of the infrastructure is to enable Open Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment (OS-aware RRA) however, at the same time, it seeks to aggregate all available open resources relevant to research assessment, helping to catalyse the development of an open, federated research-assessment dataspace that can support assessment practices more broadly.

The infrastructure is designed to be modular and scalable, allowing for the integration of new resources as needed. It is also designed to be open and accessible, enabling the research community to contribute to its development and use. The infrastructure is based on a federated architecture and is distributed across multiple locations to be more resilient and adaptable to changing needs and contexts. The architecture mainly comprises core catalogues collecting essential metadata, a Data Interoperability & Access Layer (DIAL) enhancing interoperability across federated data sources, and a web-based front-end that acts as a meta-catalogue by enriching the metadata from the core catalogues to enable advanced search and guide users in discovering relevant research assessment resources within and beyond the EOSC ecosystem. As a whole, these components establish the technical foundation for a sustainable, open, and community-driven research-assessment ecosystem.

This report details the implementation of the core components of the GraspOS infrastructure and provides references to the relevant code repositories and documentation materials. Section 2 offers the necessary background, explaining key terminology and presenting a high-level overview of the GraspOS infrastructure architecture (with further details available in D4.2¹). Section 3 elaborates on the implementation of the core components, while Section 4 provides references to the respective code bases and documentation materials. Finally, Section 5 concludes the report.

¹ D4.2 “Infrastructure architecture (v2)”: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13618530>

2. Background & Architecture Overview

Current research-assessment practices face significant challenges, such as the overreliance on opaque and often misunderstood quantitative indicators, dependence on proprietary data sources, and the narrow focus on publications while overlooking other research contributions. As a result, there is a growing recognition that assessing research and researchers needs to be done in a more responsible way², which will take into consideration (a) the values, scope, and context of each assessment event, (b) qualitative evidence supported by quantitative data and indicators, and (c) multiple aspects and merits of research work that should be acknowledged. At the same time, research assessment itself must be transparent and accountable, ensuring that evaluation criteria, data sources, and decision-making processes are open to scrutiny. Finally, since openness in science enhances both research credibility and knowledge sharing, there is a growing need for frameworks and technologies that enable *Open-Science-aware Responsible Research Assessment (OS-aware RRA)*, crediting and rewarding OS practices (along with other diverse research-related activities). This shift aligns with the principles of the CoARA Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment and with the broader European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) vision of federated, transparent, and community-driven data ecosystems.

GraspOS aims to address these issues by designing and delivering an open and federated research-assessment infrastructure. In the project plan, this infrastructure was referred to as the "Federated Open Metrics Infrastructure (FOMI)" however, for brevity, we will simply call it the *GraspOS infrastructure* from now on. The GraspOS infrastructure is designed to aggregate open resources (data, tools, services, templates, and guidance materials) that can catalyse the implementation of policy reforms towards OS-aware RRA.

Figure 1 presents a high-level conceptual architecture of the infrastructure. The project partners developed many components of the infrastructure from scratch, while also leveraging, adapting, and building upon existing systems (e.g., Zenodo, the OpenAIRE Services Catalogue) and established specifications (e.g., the RDA's SKG-IF) whenever appropriate and useful (details in Section 3). The architecture of the GraspOS infrastructure mainly consists of a set of *core catalogues* that collect basic metadata for research assessment resources; a *Data Interoperability & Access Layer (DIAL)* that improves interoperability across federated data sources; and a *web-based front-end* that provides access to the core catalogues, enriches their metadata to improve resource discoverability, and supports advanced search capabilities through a *meta-catalogue* that facilitates the discovery of valuable research-assessment resources. The front-end serves as the main entry point to the infrastructure, informing the

² CoARA, 2022, The Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. <https://coara.eu/agreement/the-agreement-full-text/>

end-users about its contents and assisting them in discovering federated resources of interest. The catalogues are also designed in a way to facilitate the discoverability of the respective resources within the EOSC ecosystem, , by ensuring that the core metadata of each resource are registered in catalogues harvested by EOSC’s EU Node Resource Hub³.

Figure 1 Overview of the GraspOS infrastructure core components

A detailed description of the initial architecture design is described in Deliverables D4.1 - “Infrastructure Architecture (v1)”⁴ and D4.2 “Infrastructure Architecture (v2)”⁵. The current report builds upon these earlier versions, documents the implementation of the software packages that compose the GraspOS infrastructure, and references their respective code bases and documentation. Earlier versions of this deliverable were published in August 2023⁶ and August 2024⁷. In this version, beyond updating the code base and documentation links accordingly, we have incorporated improvements and refinements made during the last months of the project, including updates to the implementation of the core components and to several technical specifications.

Additionally, a key architectural update introduced in this version limits the core catalogues, which in the initial design were intended to store all resource metadata, to collecting only

³ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources>

⁴ D4.1 “Infrastructure architecture (v1)”: <https://zenodo.org/records/8302198>

⁵ D4.2 “Infrastructure architecture (v2)”: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13618530>

⁶ D4.3 “Federated Open Metrics Infrastructure (v1)”: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10475567>

⁷ D4.4 “Federated Open Metrics Infrastructure (v2)”: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13617814>

basic metadata. The front-end has been extended to act as a meta-catalogue, supported by a local database that stores the complete metadata defined by the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema, including all enrichments. This redesign, implemented during the final phase of the project, reduces redundancy, enhances modularity, and substantially improves the maintainability and long-term sustainability of the infrastructure. For instance, it ensures that the schemas of the core catalogues remain closely aligned with those used by the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub, thereby facilitating seamless metadata synchronisation. Additionally, existing EOSC-synchronised systems (e.g., Zenodo, the OpenAIRE Services Catalogue) can be used to implement these core catalogues without requiring custom schema extensions (just basic configuration), which significantly eases maintenance and reduces the effort needed to keep GraspOS metadata in sync with the broader EOSC ecosystem. At the same time, the meta-catalogue captures much richer metadata related to the research-assessment domain, enabling advanced exploration functionalities tailored for research assessment use cases and delivering high-quality services to end users.

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3. Implementation

This section describes implementation details for the various core components of the GraspOS infrastructure.

3.1. Core Catalogues

The basic metadata for all resources registered in the GraspOS infrastructure are stored in a set of core catalogues, each corresponding to a specific resource type (data, tools, services, and templates/guidelines). The first list of resources included in these catalogues were resources owned by the project's technical partners; the owner of each resource registered it to the infrastructure providing the required metadata. However, the GraspOS infrastructure is planned to act as an open and evolving ecosystem; hence, the list of resources will be extended in the future, based on a clear resource inclusion policy that will be published shortly after the completion of the project (relevant insights can be found in D4.2⁸).

While the core catalogues can be accessed independently by end users, their contents, enriched with additional metadata to improve resource discoverability, are also accessible through the GraspOS infrastructure front-end, which essentially functions as a powerful meta-catalogue (see Section 3.3).

In the following sections, we first present the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema (Section 3.1.1), which defines all metadata fields required for the resources in the GraspOS infrastructure, including both the basic metadata collected by the core catalogues and the enrichments stored in the database of the meta-catalogue. Sections 3.1.2–3.1.5 then provide implementation details for each of the core catalogues.

3.1.1. GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema

The GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema⁹ was developed by the GraspOS internal Working Group on Resource Metadata Schemas. Its main goal was to define a consistent set of metadata fields that describe diverse resource types relevant to research-assessment processes and support the development of the GraspOS infrastructure catalogues. The schema is designed to include basic fields common to general-purpose scholarly catalogues (such as Zenodo or the EOSC EU Node Resource Hub), while also providing richer information

⁸ GraspOS Deliverable 4.2: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13618530>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17240298>

(a) to highlight attributes essential for the practical use of each resource, and (b) to enable advanced filtering features (called “*exploration paths*”) that improve resource discoverability within the GraspOS infrastructure.

The metadata schema applies to all the GraspOS resource types, with minor exceptions where specific fields are not relevant to a given type. Some metadata fields are covered by the core catalogues, while others represent enrichments stored by the GraspOS infrastructure front-end (which essentially serves as a meta-catalogue). For each field, the specification defines its name, description, data type, and requirement level (required, recommended, or optional). Recommended fields should ideally not be left blank, as completing them ensures accurate and discoverable resource descriptions. Each field’s short description also indicates its potential metadata source. Some fields must be completed manually by the GraspOS resource provider, while others can be automatically harvested from external sources such as Zenodo or the OpenAIRE Graph.

An asterisk-based notation is used to indicate whether a field is relevant for the “*exploration paths*” feature (i.e., advanced filtering) of the GraspOS infrastructure. A single asterisk (*) denotes fields that are central to filtering, while a double asterisk (**) marks fields used in a supporting role (e.g., for ordering results rather than filtering them).

In the following paragraphs, we present all metadata fields of the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema, grouped according to their semantic categories.

Basic information.

A set of metadata describing basic information of the resource.

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
doi	Digital object identifier representing all versions of the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo.	string	recommended ¹⁰
doi_last	Digital object identifier representing the most recent version of the resource. User provided.	string	required ¹¹
version	The most recent version of the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.version).	string	required
resource_type	Type of the resource. User provided.	controlled string ¹²	required

¹⁰ For all resource types, except services.

¹¹ For all resource types, except services.

¹² Can be “Dataset”, “Tool”, “Service”, or “Template / Guidelines”.

title	Title of resource (according to the most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.title).	string	required
description	Short description of the resource (according to the most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.description).	text	required
publication_date	Date of publication (of the most recent version) of the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.publication_date).	String - ISO8601 format (YYYY-MM-DD)	required ¹³
access_rights*	The access rights of the resource (according to the most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.access_right).	controlled string	required
license*	License that applies to the resource (according to the most recent version).	object	required
url	The main URL of the resource (e.g., a landing page providing basic info for the resource). User provided.	string - URL	optional ¹⁴
creators	The creators of the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.creators).	array of objects	required ¹⁵
contributors	The contributors of the resource (e.g., editors, curators, etc.). Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.contributors).	Array of objects	optional
keywords	Keywords describing topics related to the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.keywords).	array of strings	recommended
language*	The language of the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.language).	controlled string - ISO 639 language code implemented according to BCP 47	recommended
references	List of references. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.references).	array of strings	optional ¹⁶
adopted_standards	Various specifications adopted/implemented by the resource	array of strings	optional

¹³ For all resource types, except services.

¹⁴ Required for services.

¹⁵ For all resource types, except services.

¹⁶ Not applicable for services.

	(e.g., FAIR specs, interoperability standards). Multiple values expected for this field. User provided.		
TRL	The technology readiness level of a tool or service. Can be fetched from a local service catalogue (e.g., the OpenAIRE Service Catalogue) or it can be user provided.	integer	optional ¹⁷

Governance, sustainability, and funding.

A set of metadata describing information related to the governance, sustainability, and funding of the resource.

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
governance_model	The governance model followed for the particular resource. User provided.	text	optional
governance_bodies	The organisations or structures involved in the governance model. Their roles can be (optionally) explained in the governance_model field. User provided.	array of strings	optional
sustainability_plan	URL of digital document elaborating the sustainability plan of the resource (if available). User provided.	string - URL	optional
funding	Identification information of received funding that contributed to the creation and maintenance of the resource. Can be fetched from Zenodo (metadata.grants).	array of objects	recommended

Support.

A set of metadata offering useful information for the support options of the respective resource.

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
documentation_urls	URLs to the main documentation websites of the resource. User provided.	array of strings - URLs	recommended
training_materials	URLs to the main pages listing training material for the resource. User provided.	array of strings - URLs	optional
support_channels	Collection of helpdesk emails, forms, and community forum URLs. User	array of strings	recommended

¹⁷ Not applicable for datasets and templates & guidelines.

	provided.		
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Coverage.

A set of metadata explaining the context under which the resource is useful in research assessment and the various aspects it covers.

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
SCOPE_stages*	The SCOPE methodology stages in which the resource can be used. User provided.	array of controlled strings ¹⁸	optional
assessment_values*	A set of values that can be supported by a research assessment event using the resource. User provided.	array of strings	optional
assessment_subjects*	The research entities (e.g., individual researchers, research performing organisations, countries, etc.) of which the assessment can be supported using the resource. User provided.	array of controlled strings ¹⁹	recommended
assessment_functionalities*	Main functionality categories supported by the resource (in case of tools and services). User provided.	array of controlled strings ²⁰	recommended ²¹
evidence_types*	The types of assessment evidence (e.g., narratives, indicators, lists of contributions, badges) that the respective source is offering or leveraging. User provided.	array of controlled strings ²²	recommended
geographic_scope*	List of geographical areas that are covered by the specific resource (it may be location-agnostic). User provided.	array of controlled strings	required
covered_fields*	List of scientific fields/topics that are covered by the specific	array of strings	required

¹⁸ "Start", "Context", "Options", "Probe", "Evaluate".

¹⁹ "Researcher", "Research performing organisation", "Country", "Other".

²⁰ "Scholarly data enrichment: Missing attributes", "Scholarly data enrichment: Indicators", "Scholarly data enrichment: Missing links & semantics", "Open Science monitoring: Researchers", "Open Science monitoring: Institutions", "Open Science monitoring: Countries", "Open Science monitoring: general", "Data", "Other". The category "Data" is only applicable for services.

²¹ Non applicable for datasets, templates and guidelines.

²² "Narratives", "Indicators". "Lists of contributions", "Badges", "Other".

	resource (it may be field-agnostic). User provided.		
covered_research_products*	On which type of research products (articles, datasets, software, etc.) this resource focuses. In case of a dataset, does it provide (meta)data on different types of research products? If it is a guidance document does it provide guidelines for all types of products? User provided.	array of strings	required
temporal_coverage	The time period(s) covered by the resource. User provided.	text	optional

Equity & ethical considerations.

This category of metadata captures information on the equity and ethical considerations of a resource.

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
privacy_policy	URL to the privacy compliance notice (a digital document of some kind) detailing the respective practices including GDPR and similar guidelines. User provided.	string - URL	recommended
limitations	Text describing known limitations of the resource (e.g., regarding coverage, quality of data, etc). User provided.	text	optional
ethical_considerations	Text describing related ethical considerations (e.g., known biases, etc). User provided.	text	optional
ethics_committee	List of people contributing as ethics advisors for the resource. User provided.	array of strings	optional

Statistics.

Statistics related to the usage of the resource.

Field name	Short description	Data type	Requirement
downloads**	Resource downloads ²³ (all versions). Can be fetched from Zenodo	integer	N/A

²³ Not applicable for services.

	(stats.downloads).		
udownloads**	Resource unique downloads ²⁴ (all versions). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.unique_downloads).	integer	N/A
views**	Resource views ²⁵ (all versions). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.views).	integer	N/A
uviews**	Resource unique views ²⁶ (all versions). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.unique_views).	integer	N/A
version_downloads**	Resource downloads ²⁷ (most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.version_downloads).	integer	N/A
version_udownloads**	Resource unique downloads ²⁸ (most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.version_unique_downloads).	integer	N/A
version_views**	Resource views ²⁹ (most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.version_views).	integer	N/A
version_uviews**	Resource unique views ³⁰ (most recent version). Can be fetched from Zenodo (stats.version_unique_views).	integer	N/A
times_cited**	The number of times the resource was cited ³¹ either directly or via the main article introducing it. Can be fetched from the OpenAIRE Graph.	integer	N/A

3.1.2. Data Catalogue

The Data Catalogue (referred to as the “Data Registry” in previous reports) stores and exposes basic metadata related to data assets within the GraspOS infrastructure and enables users to discover, understand, and search for them. Similarly to the other core GraspOS catalogues, it is also integrated into the meta-catalogue implemented as part of the GraspOS front-end user interface.

²⁴ Not applicable for services.

²⁵ Views=accesses for services.

²⁶ Views=accesses for services.

²⁷ Not applicable for services.

²⁸ Not applicable for services.

²⁹ Views=accesses for services.

³⁰ Views=accesses for services.

³¹ Not applicable for services.

The datasets registered in the Graspos Data Catalogue include raw or structured data that can directly support OS-aware RRA activities or produce indicators, track records, narratives or other evidence that could be valuable in such processes. The Data Catalogue aggregates metadata for all datasets federated within the Graspos infrastructure.

The implementation of the Data Catalogue is based on a Zenodo³² community, called "Graspos Datasets".³³ Zenodo is a free and open digital archive, developed by CERN and OpenAIRE, that enables researchers to share and preserve any kind of research output, such as papers, data, software, reports, and more, supporting the principles of Open Science and open access. Zenodo communities are collaborative spaces where users can collaborate, curate, and manage research outputs. The representatives of each community can review and accept submissions from other Zenodo users. They can also customise the community metadata and information (e.g., the logo, the description). Figure 2, presents a snapshot of the Graspos Data Catalogue UI.

The screenshot shows the Zenodo interface for the 'Graspos Datasets' community. At the top, there is a search bar and navigation links for 'Communities' and 'My dashboard'. A 'Planned intervention' banner indicates a temporary unavailability on October 15th. The main header includes the 'Graspos Datasets' logo, a 'New upload' button, and links to 'Part of EU Open Research Repository', 'Project', and 'Athena Research and Innovation Center'. Below the header, there are navigation tabs for 'Records', 'Members', 'Curation policy', and 'About'. The main content area displays search results with filters on the left and a list of datasets on the right. The first dataset is 'BIP! DB: A Dataset of Impact Measures for Research Products', which is a Dataset, Open, and has 3 versions. The second dataset is 'OpenAIRE Graph Dataset', which is a Dataset, Open, and has 3 versions. The left sidebar contains filters for 'Versions', 'Access status', 'Resource types', and 'Subjects'.

³² Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/>

³³ Graspos Data Catalogue: <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-datasets>

Figure 2 The main page of the GraspOS Data Catalogue UI

To be included in the GraspOS Data Catalogue, a dataset must be registered as a “Dataset” resource within the GraspOS Datasets Zenodo community. The dataset becomes visible in the catalogue only after review and approval by a moderator, who evaluates its relevance to research assessment, the quality of its metadata, and other applicable criteria. Until now, most GraspOS datasets have been registered in the GraspOS Data Catalogue.

An initial version of the Data Catalogue was originally developed based on the Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network (CKAN)³⁴ software. The respective user interface was based on a customised version of the web interface offered by CKAN that had been deployed on a web server hosted at ATHENA RC’s data centre in Athens, Greece. From the end-user perspective, that implementation offered basic keyword search and filtering functionalities to facilitate the discoverability of data assets. From the administrator perspective, the implementation was supporting the registration, update, and refinement of datasets and data sources. Finally, the implementation was integrated with the Infrastructure Front-end UI (Section 3.6) exposing its contents via the CKAN API.

Although the initial implementation could partially meet the project’s needs, several issues emerged, leading the infrastructure implementation team to adopt a different approach:

- EOSC integration was not straightforward using the CKAN-based solution. It would have required substantial additional effort and introduced potential delays due to the need for separate agreements and other administrative steps.
- In contrast, the Zenodo-based approach, already applied to the Tools and Templates & Guidance Material Catalogues (see below), offered seamless EOSC integration, as Zenodo entries are automatically exposed through the EOSC Resource Hub³⁵. and was straightforward to extend to datasets. Maintaining a separate technology stack for the Data Catalogue would therefore have been both unreasonable and unsustainable in the long term.
- Finally, the architectural change that was introduced during the final phase of the project (see Section 2), limits the core catalogues to storing only EOSC-compliant basic metadata, while all discoverability-related metadata are now maintained in the meta-catalogue database (hosted on the same machine as the front-end). This significantly reduced the need to keep multiple metadata fields locally within each core catalogue, as most of the fields defined in the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema are now stored outside the core catalogues. This change resolved a key challenge

³⁴ CKAN: <https://ckan.org/>

³⁵ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/all>

previously encountered with Zenodo: its limited flexibility in extending the core data model.

3.1.3. Tools Catalogue

The Tools Catalogue component facilitates the discovery of GraspOS tools by collecting their basic metadata and integrating them both with the meta-catalogue (implemented as part of the GraspOS front-end user interface) and with EOSC. Its implementation is based on a dedicated Zenodo community, called “GraspOS Tools”.³⁶

The tools registered in the GraspOS Tools catalogue are stand-alone pieces of software, such as scripts, executables, libraries, or even workflows, which can be used by installing and executing them locally on a computer or computational cluster owned by the end-user to conduct a particular type of analysis and/or produce data in the context of research assessment events or related processes.

The GraspOS Tools Catalogue UI is based on Zenodo’s web interface, customised with the GraspOS logo and relevant textual descriptions. The basic searching, filtering, and ordering functionalities offered by the Zenodo platform are available to the GraspOS Tools Catalogue end users. Figure 3, presents a snapshot of the GraspOS Tools Catalogue UI.

The screenshot displays the GraspOS Tools Catalogue interface. At the top, the GraspOS logo and 'GraspOS Tools' title are visible, along with a 'New upload' button and the URL 'https://graspos.eu/'. Below the header, there are navigation options for 'Records' and 'Members'. The main content area shows search results for '6 results found', sorted by 'Newest'. Two tool entries are visible:

- BIP! Scholar Indicators Calculator**: Version 'May 28, 2024 (1.0.0)', Software, Open. Authors: Chatzopoulos, Serafeim; Vergoulis, Thanasis. Description: 'This software package contains implementations required for the calculation of the researcher-level indicators (mostly related to citation-based impact) that are being used by the BIP! Scholar service.' Part of GraspOS Tools. Uploaded on May 28, 2024. 41 views, 5 downloads.
- BIP! NDR Workflow**: Version 'May 28, 2024 (1.0.0)', Software, Open. Authors: Koloveas, Paris; Chatzopoulos, Serafeim; Tryfonopoulos, Christos; and 1 other. Description: 'This software includes the computational workflow that is able to create the various versions of the BIP! NDR dataset. In the field of Computer Science, conference and workshop papers serve as important contributions, carrying substantial weight in research assessment processes, compared to other disciplines. However, a considerable number of...'

Figure 3 The main page of the GraspOS Tools Catalogue UI

³⁶ GraspOS Tools Catalogue: <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-tools>

Based on this implementation, each GraspOS tool is expected to be registered to this community creating a “Software” entry. Each tool provider is required to provide values for all mandatory fields for Zenodo software entries. The tool record will only appear in the community after it has been reviewed and approved by a moderator, who evaluates its relevance to research assessment, the quality of its metadata, and other applicable criteria.

For tool versioning, the current approach mandates publishing a new version of the respective Zenodo software entry whenever significant changes are made to the respective tool. However, an option to streamline this process leveraging connections between Zenodo and GitHub³⁷ is offered to the tool owners after appropriate configuration.³⁸

Until now, most GraspOS tools have been registered in the GraspOS Tools Catalogue. Since Zenodo is harvested by OpenAIRE for inclusion in the OpenAIRE Graph³⁹, which is the basis for the research software entries in the the Resource Hub of the EOSC EU Node,⁴⁰ all GraspOS tools will be discoverable through EOSC’s main discovery platform. Finally, the end user can leverage the advanced search and browsing capabilities already provided by Zenodo to its users to perform advanced searching. As it is evident, after identifying a tool of interest, the end user will need a computational system to run it and some basic technical skills to install/deploy it.

3.1.4. Services Catalogue

The Services Catalogue component collects the metadata of all GraspOS services. The services listed in the GraspOS Services Catalogue are pieces of software that provide a set of functions or features for the end user, which can be helpful in the context of research assessment processes. These services are typically hosted on a remote server or cluster and accessed via a web interface or API. The service providers aim to offer them in a 24/7 manner giving guarantees for the respective Quality of Service (QoS), such as the service availability. The GraspOS Services Catalogue also facilitates the integration of the previous services into the EOSC ecosystem. Finally, similar to the other core catalogues, the GraspOS Services Catalogue is integrated into the meta-catalogue implemented as part of the GraspOS infrastructure front-end.

³⁷ <https://zenodo.org/account/settings/github/>

³⁸ <https://help.zenodo.org/docs/github/archive-software/github-upload/>

³⁹ The OpenAIRE Graph: <https://graph.openaire.eu/>

⁴⁰ EOSC EU Node Resource Hub: <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/resources/all>

The Services Catalogue is based on the OpenAIRE Catalogue open-source software platform.⁴¹ The backend of the OpenAIRE Catalogue is implemented in Java using the Spring Boot framework⁴², ensuring a scalable and efficient foundation that guarantees not only reliability but also swift responses to user queries and dynamic updates. Its frontend, on the other hand, is implemented in Angular⁴³ and delivers a responsive, and dynamic user interface. The Angular framework facilitates the creation of a seamless and interactive user interface, enabling intuitive navigation and exploration of the available service. Users can search, filter, and discover pertinent information about each service effortlessly, enhancing their overall engagement. A screenshot of the main page of the catalogue can be found in Figure 4.

Figure 4 Screenshot of the main page of the GraspOS Services Catalogue

⁴¹ The OpenAIRE Catalogue: <https://github.com/madgeek-arc/resource-catalogue-ui-openaire> & <https://github.com/madgeek-arc/openaire-catalogue>

⁴² Spring Boot framework: <https://spring.io/projects/spring-boot>

⁴³ Angular: <https://angular.dev/>

The GraspOS service catalogue uses the set of mandatory metadata fields from the OpenAIRE catalogue data model. For reference, Table 1 outlines these fields together with descriptions about their interpretations and data types.

Table 1 *GraspOS Services metadata model*

Field name	Description	Type
Name	Brief & descriptive name of the Resource given by the Provider.	string
Abbreviation	Abbreviation or short name of the Resource.	string
Resource organisation	The organisation name that manages or delivers the resource, or coordinates the Resource delivery in a federated scenario.	related organisation
Webpage	Web page with information about the resource, usually hosted and maintained by the provider.	hyperlink
Tagline	Short catchphrase for marketing and advertising purposes. It will usually be displayed close to the Resource name and should refer to the main value or purpose of the Resource.	text
Short description	The pitch deck. Follows a specific wording: [Name of service] is a [what] that does [how] For [who] By	text
Long description	A high-level description in fairly non-technical terms of a) what the Resource does, functionality it provides and Resources it enables to access, b) the benefit to a user/customer delivered by a Resource; benefits are usually related to alleviating pains (e.g., eliminate undesired outcomes, obstacles or risks) or producing gains (e.g. increased performance, social gains, positive emotions or cost saving), c) list of customers, communities, users, etc. using the Resource.	text
Logo	Link to the logo/visual identity of the Resource. The logo will be visible at the Portal. If there is no specific logo for the Resource the logo of the Provider may be used. Go to the Resource Provider's website --> Right Click on the Resource Provider's logo on the website --> Select "Copy Image Link" --> Paste it in the below field.	hyperlink to logo image
Scientific domain	The branch of science, scientific discipline that is related to the Resource.	Controlled value
Scientific subdomain	The sub-branch of science, scientific subdiscipline that is related to the Resource.	Controlled value
Category	A named group of Resources that offer access to the same type of Resources.	Controlled value
Subcategory	A named group of Resources that offer access to the same type of Resources, within the defined Resource category.	Controlled value

Target users	Type of users that commissions a Provider to deliver a Resource.	Controlled value
Geographical availability	Locations where the Resource is offered.	string - Please specify a list of countries or "Worldwide"
Language availability	Languages of the (user interface of the) Resource.	string - Please specify a list of languages
Main contact - First Name	First Name of the Resource's main contact person/Resource manager.	string
Main contact - Last Name	Last Name of the Resource's main contact person/Resource manager.	string
Main contact - Email	Email of the Resource's main contact person/Resource manager.	email
Public contact - Email	Email of the Resource's contact person or a generic email of the Provider to be displayed publicly at the Portal.	email
Helpdesk - Email	The email to ask more information from the Provider about the Resource.	email
Security contact - Email	The email to contact the Provider for critical security issues about the Resource.	email
Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	The Technology Readiness Level of the Resource.	Controlled value
Terms of use	Webpage describing the rules, Resource conditions and usage policy which one must agree to abide by in order to use the Resource.	hyperlink
Privacy policy	Link to the privacy policy applicable to the Resource.	hyperlink
Order type	Information on the ordering process type.	Controlled value
Documentation	Service documentation page.	hyperlink
Banner Image	Vertical image that will be displayed as a banner on the main page	hyperlink
Card Image	Image that will be displayed on cards when the resource is shown as a related service.	hyperlink

During the development phase of the GraspOS Catalogue, a local deployment of the OpenAIRE Catalogue, hosted on an ATHENA's server in Athens (Greece), is used. In the future, an EOSC-synchronised deployment will be used (maybe the main deployment of the OpenAIRE Catalogue, but this will be subject of future agreements).

3.1.5. Templates & Guidance Material Catalogue

The aim of this component is to collect basic metadata related to resources facilitating the research assessment process, including:

- **templates for documents**, which can be used during the research assessment process, such as templates for documenting the assessment readiness, stakeholder mapping, value and/or purpose statement of the respective research assessment events, or similar resources (see also Section 4 of D2.2 "OSAF"⁴⁴) including academic profile/CV templates.
- **guidance documents**, which can inform readers on subjects related to responsible and OS-aware research assessment, such as the Open Science Assessment Guide⁴⁵ and the EDI guide⁴⁶ introduced by GraspOS WP2 (see also Section 4 of D2.2).
- **checklists**, which are systematic lists of steps arranged in a specific order, used as a tool to ensure that all necessary actions for research assessment processes are taken and nothing is overlooked (see also Section 4 of D2.2).
- **indicator toolboxes**, which are comprehensive collections of metrics and indicators designed to estimate various aspects of research performance, impact, and quality (see also Section 4 of D2.2).

Similarly to the Data and Tools Catalogues, the Templates & Guidance Material Catalogue is implemented as a dedicated Zenodo community⁴⁷ that collects the previous types of resources. As with all core GraspOS catalogues it is integrated into the meta-catalogue that is implemented as part of the GraspOS front-end user interface and the EOSC ecosystem (all resources are searchable via the EOSC Resource Hub). Figure 5 presents a snapshot of the GraspOS Templates & Guidance Catalogue UI.

⁴⁴ GraspOS Deliverable 2.2: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10475459>

⁴⁵ <https://zenodo.org/records/15525630>

⁴⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15526121>

⁴⁷ GraspOS Tools & Guidelines Catalogue: <https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-assessment-process-resources>

graspOS open research assessment dataspace

GraspOS Templates & Guidelines

Part of EU Open Research Repository <https://graspOS.eu/> Project
Athena Research and Innovation Center In Information Communication & Knowledge Technologies
ROR and 15 more organizations

Records Members Curation policy About

1 results found Sort by Newest

June 21, 2025 (1.0) Report Open

Key Components of Researcher Profiles in Computer Science
Vergoulis, Thanasis; Chatzopoulos, Serafeim; Romary, Laurent; and 4 others

This report provides an overview of a broad set of components that are relevant to academic profiles of researchers in the field of Computer Science (CS). Each component corresponds to a specific type of research activity or career achievement which can be supplemented with...

Part of EU Open Research Repository, GraspOS Templates & Guidelines
Uploaded on August 27, 2025

20 19

Figure 5 The main page of the GraspOS Templates & Guidance Catalogue UI

To be included in the GraspOS Templates & Guidance Material Catalogue, a resource must be registered as a “Publication/Report” or “Publication/Other” resource within the respective Zenodo community. The resource will only appear in the community after it has been reviewed and approved by a moderator, who evaluates its relevance to research assessment, the quality of its metadata, and other applicable criteria. Until now, most GraspOS resources that can be classified as templates or guidance materials have been registered to the GraspOS Templates & Guidance Material Catalogue.

3.2. Data Interoperability & Access Layer (DIAL)

In the following sections, we elaborate on the design and implementation of the GraspOS Data Interoperability & Access Layer.

3.2.1. The Concept

The GraspOS infrastructure contains a “Data Interoperability and Access Layer” (called “DIAL” for brevity) which aims to facilitate the integration and harmonisation of (meta)data from various sources and formats within the infrastructure. This component aims to ease the work of developers in implementing tools and value-added services on top of the respective data sources.

GraspOS DIAL essentially comprises the union of all API endpoints that offer access to the contents of the (federated) data sources included in the GraspOS infrastructure. During the lifetime of the project, all data sources are expected to make efforts towards the development

of API endpoints that are compatible and interoperable with each other. To achieve this, GraspOS builds upon widely accepted standards, most notably the RDA's⁴⁸ Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework⁴⁹ (SKG-IF). To coordinate this activity, GraspOS has created an "Internal Working Group on Data Interoperability and Access", whose main output is the GraspOS data model and API specification, an official extension of SKG-IF called "RA-SKG"⁵⁰, specifically tailored for research assessment applications.

3.2.2. GraspOS Data Model & API Specification Design

Preliminary work on the development of the GraspOS data model and API specification took place in early stages of the project (reported in Deliverables D4.2 and D4.4). However, following this preliminary work, the internal working group adopted a structured approach to develop the corresponding data model and API specification. More specifically, the SAMOD methodology⁵¹ was adopted. SAMOD is an abbreviation for Simplified Agile Methodology for Ontology Development, and it represents a novel agile methodology for the development of ontologies by means of small steps of an iterative workflow that focuses on creating well-developed and documented models starting from exemplar domain descriptions.

In the case of creating RA-SKG, the GraspOS model and API specification, the team was split into two groups. The first group was created by domain experts, i.e. people with some experience in the research assessment process. The second group was created by model engineers. The task assigned to the first group was to write motivating scenarios. After a couple of meetings and discussion about motivating scenarios, the team decided to work on two motivating scenarios:

1. Academic profiles for researchers
2. Indicators for monitoring Research Performing Organisations

Basic description of those scenarios (including examples)⁵² has been provided by the first group (domain experts), as well as informal competency questions⁵³ for those scenarios. The second group (model engineers) created glossaries⁵⁴ based on scenarios descriptions and

⁴⁸ Research Data Alliance (RDA): <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁴⁹ Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework (SKG-IF): <https://skg-if.github.io/>

⁵⁰ <https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/>

⁵¹ <https://essepuntato.it/samod/>

⁵² Scenario 1: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/01/development/01_motivating-scenario, Scenario 2: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/02/development/01_motivating-scenario

⁵³ Scenario 1: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/01/development/02_informal-competency-questions, Scenario 2: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/02/development/02_informal-competency-questions

⁵⁴ Scenario 1: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/01/development/03_glossary, Scenario 2: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/02/development/03_glossary

linked informal competency questions, diagrams⁵⁵, formal model⁵⁶ as a TBOX expressed in the turtle notation, sample data⁵⁷ as an ABOX expressed in the turtle notation, formal representation of competency queries⁵⁸, and conducted tests⁵⁹ on whether the created model is capable of providing responses to queries.

By creation of all resources mentioned above, a “modelet” has been created for each motivating scenario. A modelet is a stand-alone model supporting a particular motivating scenario. Model engineers after creation of modelet for each motivating scenario, conducted merging of modelet with the core SKG-IF model and producing the GraspOS data model, i.e., the RA-SKG extension. At the end, model engineers refactored and optimized the final RA-SKG model.

The RA-SKG Data Model extends the SKG-IF Data Model with additional classes, their attributes and their relations to other entities. All these aspects are implemented using the ‘language’ of the Semantic Web, in particular by re-employing several existing ontological models developed to address specific modelling scenarios compatible with the aims of this extension.

3.2.3. The GraspOS Data Model (RA-SKG)

The RA-SKG Data Model, summarised in the Graffoo diagram⁶⁰ presented in Figure 6 allows one to record information which are required for research assessment use cases, as well as their relationships with well-established entities of the scholarly communication domain. Examples of such entities are research performance indicators, which are used to support various research evaluation processes, and narrative CVs, which are texts presenting the overarching story of one or more research products usually related to an entity of interest.

⁵⁵ Scenario 1: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/01/development/04_diagram, Scenario 2: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/02/development/04_diagram

⁵⁶ Scenario 1: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/01/development/05_TBox, Scenario 2: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/02/development/05_TBox

⁵⁷ Scenario 1: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/01/development/06_ABox, Scenario 2: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/02/development/06_ABox

⁵⁸ Scenario 1: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/01/development/07_formal_competency_questions, Scenario 2: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/02/development/07_formal_competency_questions

⁵⁹ Scenario 1: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/01/development/08_formal_testing, Scenario 2: https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/data-model/samod/02/development/08_formal_testing

⁶⁰ <https://essepuntato.it/graffoo>

The SKG-IF data created following the RA-SKG extension of the SKG-IF⁶² are aligned with the SKG-IF Ontology: Research Assessment extension via the SKG-IF JSON-LD context⁶³ extended with the RA-SKG JSON-LD context⁶⁴. In addition, a specific SHACL document⁶⁵ has been developed for semantically validating the data provided according to the data model of this extension.

RA-SKG extends these core entities:

- The core Research product⁶⁶ entity, introducing metrics (i.e., indicators and badges) resulting in an extended RA-SKG Research product⁶⁷ entity.
- The core Agent⁶⁸ entity, introducing metrics (i.e., indicators and badges) and profiles, resulting in an extended RA-SKG Agent⁶⁹ entity.

3.2.4. The GraspOS API Specification

The SKG-IF core model includes an associated API specification⁷⁰. Building on this, RA-SKG was used to develop a corresponding API specification⁷¹ by applying an OpenAPI overlay to the core specification, enabling support for the extensions introduced by RA-SKG. This resulting specification is referred to as the GraspOS API Specification or the RA-SKG OpenAPI Specification.

The GraspOS API specification is designed to facilitate data exchange and interoperability between onboarded metadata sources and value-added services. It enables users to explore the various entities, facilitating structured metadata retrieval for different types of research-related information.

The API provides endpoints for all core entities of SKG-IF, as extended by RA-SKG, offering two endpoints per entity:

- One for retrieving a single record by its unique identifier,
- One for searching multiple records using filters.

These endpoints enable seamless interaction with GraspOS services while maintaining compatibility with the broader RA-SKG ecosystem.

⁶² <https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/extended-interoperability-framework/ra-skg-if.html>

⁶³ <https://w3id.org/skg-if/context/skg-if.json>

⁶⁴ <https://w3id.org/skg-if/extension/ra-skg/context/skg-if.json>

⁶⁵ <https://w3id.org/skg-if/extension/ra-skg/validation/shacl>

⁶⁶ <https://skg-if.github.io/interoperability-framework/docs/research-product.html>

⁶⁷ <https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/extended-interoperability-framework/core-extensions/ra-skg-research-product.html>

⁶⁸ <https://skg-if.github.io/interoperability-framework/docs/agent.html>

⁶⁹ <https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/extended-interoperability-framework/core-extensions/ra-skg-agent.html>

⁷⁰ <https://skg-if.github.io/api/>

⁷¹ <https://skg-if.github.io/ext-ra-skg/api/api.html>

API endpoints for retrieving a single entity using its unique identifier.

Each entity type has a dedicated endpoint following the pattern:

```
GET {base_url}/api/{entity_type}/{local_identifier}
```

where `base_url` is the base URL of the API, `entity_type` is the type of entity (e.g., product, person, etc.), and `local_identifier` is the unique identifier of the entity.

Below is a list of the available single-entity endpoints:

- Research Products - `/api/products/{local_identifier}`
- Agents:
 - `/api/persons/{local_identifier}`
 - `/api/organisations/{local_identifier}`
- Grants - `/api/grants/{local_identifier}`
- Venues - `/api/venues/{local_identifier}`
- Topics - `/api/topics/{local_identifier}`
- Data Sources - `/api/datasources/{local_identifier}`
- Grants - `/api/grants/{local_identifier}`

The data of a single entity can be retrieved by providing the entity's local identifier in the corresponding endpoint.

The response for a single entity request will return the entity's data in JSON format. The structure of the response will depend on the entity type, and can be one of the following: Product, Agent, Grant, Venue, Topic, or Data source.

API endpoints for entity searching.

The specification provides endpoints for retrieving multiple records of various entities, allowing users to search entities based on specific criteria. The following endpoints are available for searching:

- Research Products - `/api/products`
- Agents:
 - `/api/persons`
 - `/api/organisations`
- Grants - `/api/grants`
- Venues - `/api/venues`
- Topics - `/api/topics`
- Data Sources - `/api/datasources`
- Grants - `/api/grants`

Each endpoint enables the retrieval of all instances of the respective entity, supporting entity-specific filtering along with common request parameters for pagination and sorting. More details on the various request parameters can be found in the respective documentation page⁷².

Each API response follows a standardised JSON format, including a common header segment that provides metadata about the search results:

```
{
  "meta": {
    "count": 100,
    "page": 1,
    "page_size": 10
  },
  "results": [ ... ]
}
```

The `meta` object in the response contains the following properties:

- `count` - Total number of results matching the query.
- `page` - Current page number.
- `page_size` - Number of results returned per page.

Finally, the `results` field contains an array of entity objects, as described in the RA-SKG, matching the query.

3.2.5. Implementation Plans & Status

In the context of GraspOS, the data service providers are building upon the aforementioned data model and API specification to make the required changes from their side and (a) support data snapshots aligned to the RA-SKG model, and (b) deploy RA-SKG-compliant API endpoints so that their sources will be federated more easily. Currently, many GraspOS data service providers have started the respective work (e.g., OpenAIRE, ARC, UNIBO), with some of them having tangible outputs. Indicatively, OpenAIRE has released an OpenAIRE Graph dataset that is compliant to the RA-SKG and is working on providing RA-SKG-compliant Graph API endpoints; ARC has created RA-SKG-compliant endpoints for the BIP! DB API (including an

⁷² <https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/apis/search-api/searching-for-entities>

endpoint for BIP! NDR data); UNIBO has started working on providing RA-SKG-compliant API endpoints for OpenCitations.

3.3. Infrastructure Front-end & Meta-catalogue

This component serves as the entry point of the GraspOS infrastructure. It consists of (a) a basic web user interface (UI) informing end-users about the infrastructure's contents and specifications, providing easy access to the core catalogues, and (b) a meta-catalogue that collects rich metadata for research assessment resources and offers advanced search and filtering capabilities. In the next sections, we elaborate on both subcomponents.

3.3.1. Basic Web UI

The basic Web UI⁷³ is a front-end user interface (UI) that can inform GraspOS end-users about the GraspOS infrastructure contents (components, resources, etc), relevant technologies, and specifications, while also helping them navigate between the various catalogues (core and meta) of the GraspOS infrastructure. This UI is essentially the entry point to the infrastructure.

Its implementation is based on Docusaurus,⁷⁴ a framework for building and deploying customised and highly optimised project websites. It leverages Markdown to add the website's content, thus simplifying the authoring process and enabling content writers lacking technical background to focus on delivering high-quality, informative content without a steep learning curve.

The front-end UI is highly adaptable and responsive, thanks to Docusaurus's built-in support for mobile devices. It offers a consistent and user-friendly experience across a wide range of devices, ensuring that the content scales seamlessly to fit different screen sizes. It also supports embedding dynamic code, enabling the implementation of advanced interactive features. Last but not least, its built-in support for versioning and several deployment additions/plugins have streamlined our website's maintenance process, allowing us to effortlessly update content and deploy changes promptly.

A snapshot of the main page of the basic Web UI is illustrated in Figure 7. The page displays key information related to the GraspOS infrastructure and provides links to the core catalogues and the meta-catalogue (accessible via the "Search" option in the top-right corner).

⁷³ GraspOS Infrastructure front-end UI: <https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/>

⁷⁴ Docusaurus: <https://github.com/facebook/docusaurus>

The following subsection describes the meta-catalogue in greater detail, including its metadata model and search functionalities.

Figure 7 Snapshot of the basic Web UI

3.3.2. Meta-catalogue

The GraspOS meta-catalogue⁷⁵ refers to a module that consists of (a) a database that collects the full metadata according to the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema for all GraspOS resources, (b) a web UI that allows registered users to add or edit resources in the meta-catalogue, and (c) a public web interface that allows all users to search for research-assessment resources. In the next paragraphs, we elaborate on each of the aforementioned sub-modules. It is worth mentioning that a detailed user manual describing the meta-catalogue's functionalities is openly available on Zenodo.⁷⁶

3.3.2.1. META-CATALOGUE DATABASE

The Meta-Catalogue stores its data in a MongoDB⁷⁷ database, offering flexibility for representing diverse and evolving catalogue records. Database interactions are handled

⁷⁵ <https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/catalogue/>

⁷⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17339364>

⁷⁷ <https://www.mongodb.com/>

through Beanie⁷⁸, an asynchronous Object Document Mapper (ODM) built on top of Motor⁷⁹ and Pydantic⁸⁰, ensuring efficient query execution and schema validation. This setup allows the system to take full advantage of FastAPI's asynchronous capabilities, maintaining high performance even under multiple concurrent requests. The underlying data model implements the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema (see Section 3.1.1). It captures the hierarchical and interconnected nature of research resources. Appropriate indexing and validation at the database level ensure data integrity and rapid retrieval.

3.3.2.2. META-CATALOGUE ADMINISTRATION UI

The administration section of the meta-catalogue is accessible only to registered users. This restricted section allows users to register new resources or edit existing resource details. Anyone wishing to perform these actions must first create an account and sign in to the GraspOS infrastructure.

Any registered user can add a new resource to the GraspOS infrastructure meta-catalogue. The process involves filling in the resource metadata according to the latest version of the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema. This is a two-step process:

1. First, the user creates an entry for the resource in the respective GraspOS core catalogue (for Data, Tools, and Templates / Guidelines, the catalogue is based on a Zenodo community; for Services, the catalogue is based on a deployment of the OpenAIRE Service Catalogue).
2. Then, the user registers the respective core catalogue entry into the GraspOS infrastructure user interface and enriches the entry with additional metadata according to the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema. Figure 8 illustrates the main resource registration form.

⁷⁸ <https://beanie-odm.dev/>

⁷⁹ <https://motor.readthedocs.io/>

⁸⁰ <https://docs.pydantic.dev/latest/>

Figure 8 Main resource registration form

Once the metadata is submitted, the resource does not become publicly available immediately. Instead, a notification is sent to a GraspOS moderator, who reviews the submission to ensure it meets the basic requirements of the GraspOS inclusion policy (e.g., related to the completeness and quality of the metadata, the relevance of the resource to the scope of the infrastructure). Moderators can either approve, request revisions, or reject submissions that do not align with the inclusion criteria. After the moderator approval, the respective resource becomes published in the GraspOS infrastructure.

Additionally, each registered user has the ability to edit or delete any entry they have created. When editing an entry, the user is allowed to modify any metadata field of the resource that is not harvested by the respective core catalogue. If a change is needed for the harvested fields, the respective core catalogue entry should be edited via the core catalogue user interface. Similarly, when deleting an entry, only the meta-catalogue entry is deleted, not the respective core catalogue record.

The UI for the administration of the meta-catalogue is implemented using React⁸¹, providing a modern, modular, and responsive front-end experience. The application is bootstrapped with Vite⁸² for fast development as well as optimized builds, while Material-UI⁸³ (MUI) is used to ensure a consistent and accessible design across all pages. The interface supports intuitive navigation and user-friendly forms for managing catalogue entries. The use of React hooks and state management enables dynamic content rendering and seamless interaction with the backend API, resulting in a smooth and responsive user experience.

3.3.2.3. META-CATALOGUE SEARCH UI

The search section of the meta-catalogue interface is openly accessible to all users, whether registered or not. It offers advanced search functionalities to facilitate resource discoverability. The UI is developed with React and Material (MUI) frameworks, as detailed in Section 3.3.2.2. A snapshot of the main search interface of the GraspOS infrastructure is illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9: The main search interface of the GraspOS infrastructure with key sections highlighted

There are four key sections in this user interface:

⁸¹ <https://react.dev/>

⁸² <https://vite.dev/>

⁸³ <https://mui.com/material-ui/>

- **Keyword Search Section (blue box):** Contains the search box where users can enter keywords to retrieve relevant resources.
- **Search Results Section (green box):** Displays a list of resources that match the user-provided keywords and meet the criteria defined through the Exploration Paths and Additional Search Options.
- **Exploration Paths Section (magenta box):** Provides various useful facets that help users refine the specific characteristics of the resources they want to discover.
- **Additional Search Options Section (orange box):** Offers extra filters and sorting options to further narrow down the search results, ensuring they are tailored to the user's needs.

It should be noted that the various facets and filters rely on specific metadata fields, hence more details related to their semantics can be found in the GraspOS Resource Metadata Schema. Additionally, it is worth mentioning that each record in the search results section is represented by a compact item that summarises the most important metadata fields. To display all metadata fields of a particular resource of interest, the user needs to be redirected to the resource details page by clicking on the title hyperlink of the resource. A screenshot of the details page of a particular resource is illustrated in Figure 10.

The screenshot shows the details page for the resource 'BIP! DB: A Dataset of Impact Measures for Research Products'. The page is divided into several sections:

- Header:** Title 'BIP! DB: A Dataset of Impact Measures for Research Products' with a share icon.
- Metadata:** 'Dataset' type, version '19.1 (16 October 2025)', DOI '10.5281/zenodo.17339284', access rights 'open', license 'cc-zero', TRL 'N/A', and language 'N/A'. Keywords include 'Scientometrics', 'Research assessment', and 'Research impact'.
- Statistics:** 7709 views, 10621 downloads, and 0 citations. A 'SHOW MORE' link is present.
- Overview:** A text block describing the dataset's purpose and the types of impact indicators it includes.
- Influence indicators:** A section explaining 'Citation Count' and 'PageRank score'.
- Popularity indicators:** A section explaining the 'RAM score'.
- Coverage:** A sidebar section showing 'Subjects: -', 'Products: articles, datasets, software, other', 'Evidence: Indicators', 'Fields: Field Agnostic', 'Values: Scientific impact', 'Functionalities: -', 'Geographical Scope: -', and 'Temporal Coverage: -'.
- Support:** A sidebar section with a 'Documentation' dropdown menu containing links to 'bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/site/indicators' and 'doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4386934', and other options like 'Training material' and 'Support channel'.
- Footer:** A grid of dropdown menus for 'Authors', 'Contributors', 'Governance, Sustainability & Funding', and 'Equity & Ethical Considerations'.

Figure 10: Screenshot of the details page of a GraspOS infrastructure resource

This search interface forms the primary entry point for exploring resources within the GraspOS infrastructure, supporting both simple keyword queries and advanced, metadata-driven filtering.

4. Code Repositories & Implementation

This section provides references to the code bases of the GraspOS infrastructure’s core components and their corresponding documentation.

4.1. GraspOS Registries & Catalogues

The following table lists the code repositories, current deployments, and documentation websites of all core infrastructure components. The vast majority of those codes are maintained by ARC.

Table 2 GraspOS Registries & Catalogues Overview

Component	Code repository	Current deployment	Documentation
Infrastructure Front-end UI	https://github.com/athenarc/graspos-infra	https://graspos-infra.at henarc.gr/	https://github.com/athenarc/graspos-infra/blob/master/README.md https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17339364
Data Registry	N/A	https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-datasets/	N/A
Services Catalogue	Front-end: https://github.com/athenarc/graspos-services-catalogue-frontend Back-end: https://github.com/athenarc/graspos-services-catalogue-backend	https://graspos-services.athenarc.gr/home	https://github.com/athenarc/graspos-services-catalogue-frontend/blob/master/README.md
Tools Catalogue	N/A	https://zenodo.org/	N/A

		mmunities/graspos-tools	
Templates & Guidance Materials Catalogue	N/A	https://zenodo.org/communities/graspos-assessment-process-resources/	N/A

The Tools Catalogue, Data Registry, and Templates & Guidance Materials Catalogue have been implemented as Zenodo communities; therefore, no source-code development or additional documentation was required.

4.2. Data Interoperability & Access Layer (DIAL)

As mentioned earlier, DIAL is more or less the union of the APIs of the data services federated in the GraspOS infrastructure. As a result, no separate code repository is provided for it. The following table provides links to the APIs of the GraspOS data services as well as the repositories that contain the code for the production of the respective data assets and the respective documentation websites.

Table 3 GraspOS Data Services APIs, Production Code and Documentation

API	Data production workflow	Documentation
Assessment Protocol Registry: N/A	N/A	N/A
Assessment Portfolio Registry: N/A	N/A	N/A
BIP! DB: https://bip-api.imsi.athenarc.gr/documentation	https://github.com/athenarc/Bip-Ranker	https://github.com/athenarc/Bip-Ranker/blob/main/README.md
BIP! NDR: https://bip-api.imsi.athenarc.gr/documentation#/NDR%20-%20RA-SKG	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-ndr-workflow	https://github.com/athenarc/bip-ndr-workflow/blob/main/README.md
OpenAIRE Graph: https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-hadoop	https://graph.openaire.eu/docs/

apis/search-api/		
OpenCitations Data: https://opencitations.net/index/api/v2	https://github.com/opencitations/index and https://github.com/opencitations/oc_meta	https://github.com/opencitations/index/blob/master/README.md and https://github.com/opencitations/oc_meta/blob/master/README.md
ScholarXplorer: https://api.scholexplorer.openaire.eu/v2/ui/	https://code-repo.d4science.org/D-Net/dnet-applications/src/branch/master/apps/scholexplorer-api	https://scholexplorer.openaire.eu/documentation
PRISM: N/A	Metadata extraction through this link. Supports isolating books with PRISM record: https://www.doabooks.org/en/librarians/metadata-harvesting-and-content-dissemination	Generic documentation on how a publisher can join DOAB/PRISM: https://doabooks.org/en/publishers/documentation

4.3. Infrastructure Front-end UI

The following table presents the code repository, current deployment, and documentation of the Infrastructure Front-end UI.

Table 4 Code Repository , Deployment and Documentation of the Infrastructure Front-end UI

Component	Code repository	Current deployment	Documentation
Infrastructure front-end UI	https://github.com/athenarc/graspos-infra	https://graspos-infra.athenarc.gr/	https://github.com/athenarc/graspos-infra/blob/master/README.md

DRAFT

5. Conclusions

This report has presented the implementation details of the GraspOS infrastructure. The infrastructure comprises:

- (a) core catalogues that collect essential metadata for research-assessment resources (datasets, tools, services, templates, and guidance materials);
- (b) a Data Interoperability and Access Layer (DIAL) that enhances interoperability across federated data sources; and
- (c) a web-based front-end that acts as a meta-catalogue, enriching metadata, enabling advanced search functionalities, and guiding users in discovering research-assessment resources within and beyond the EOSC ecosystem.

The infrastructure primarily focuses on resources that can support Open Science (OS)-aware Responsible Research Assessment (RRA) processes, paving the way for policy reforms toward a responsible research-assessment framework that fully integrates Open Science principles.

In the future, the GraspOS infrastructure is expected to operate as an open and evolving ecosystem. Consequently, the list of assessment resources currently included will continue to evolve, guided by a transparent resource-inclusion policy that will be published shortly after the project's completion (with preliminary insights available in D4.2⁸⁴). This means that additional resources are expected to be integrated into the GraspOS infrastructure in the near future.

⁸⁴ GraspOS Deliverable 4.2: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13618530>